

Advancing monitoring of plankton and other pelagic organisms for marine biodiversity policy implementation

To support the effective implementation of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Water Framework Directive (WFD), Habitats and Birds Directives (HBD), and the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, **OBAMA-NEXT scientists recommend policymakers at EU and Member State levels to consider the following recommendations:**

- ◆ Make all efforts to integrate small and underrepresented size fractions into plankton assessments
- ◆ Promote the exploitation of all phytoplankton long-term datasets
- ◆ Establish common standards and guidelines for plankton and pelagic fish data collection and processing if using new technologies
- ◆ Support and advance the development of policy-relevant and fit-for-purpose indicators using new technologies
- ◆ Make sure that new monitoring tools are ready for policy uptake
- ◆ Support experts to improve interoperability of tools and data across regions

Pelagic biodiversity includes a great diversity of organisms, from plankton to fish, as well as mammals, among others. **Plankton represents an important component of pelagic biodiversity.** It is mostly composed of microscopic organisms living primarily in the water column and includes both plants and animals. Plankton species **form the base or first levels of marine food webs** and are **essential indicators of ecosystem health.** Plankton is referenced in the MSFD and the WFD, which rely on plankton data to assess the status and trends in biodiversity and food web dynamics, and eutrophication. However, the **current monitoring efforts fall often short in capturing the full diversity and functional roles of plankton communities**, particularly the smaller size fractions, such as picoplankton and nanoplankton (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Example of diversity and size range of plankton organisms (from picoplankton to macrozooplankton).

Despite rapid advances in monitoring technologies, practical challenges persist. **Data collection remains inconsistent, with multiple sampling devices, multiple standards, and limited spatial and temporal coverage across European seas.** These shortcomings compromise the comparability and policy relevance of collected data and reduce the effectiveness of biodiversity assessments under frameworks such as the MSFD and WFD, and emerging restoration targets for marine ecosystems at the Member State level defined in the EU Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR).

Relevance of pelagic monitoring tools for policy implementation

Pelagic monitoring tools provide valuable biological, functional, and spatial information while tracking changes over time, which is essential for supporting the implementation of various EU marine environmental policies and legislations.

- **Phytoplankton biomass and seasonal dynamics**, measured by autonomous instruments on different types of platforms providing validation for remote sensing measurements and knowledge on ecological status under the WFD and descriptors such as Eutrophication for MSFD.
- **Pelagic diversity**, captured through eDNA, automated flow cytometry and automated imaging, support assessments of biodiversity and habitat quality (MSFD Descriptor 1).
- **Size spectra and food web structure**, derived from advanced imaging and optics, inform food web integrity (MSFD Descriptor 4)
- **Spatiotemporal patterns of pelagic biodiversity**, observed through autonomous platforms and Earth Observation, could provide valuable data for the design, manage, and evaluation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) effectiveness and support reporting under regional sea conventions (e.g. OSPAR, HELCOM).

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OBAMA-NEXT contributions to policy-relevant data needs

The OBAMA-NEXT project has developed a series of information products (IP) to address key data needs and gaps that limit the effective implementation of EU Biodiversity Strategy and marine environmental policies. These contributions focus on improving standardisation, harmonisation, and monitoring of plankton across multiple scales and regions.

- The **position paper on eDNA use for stakeholders** consolidated expert consensus across four EU projects (OBAMA-NEXT, BIOcean5D, MARCO-BOLO, MARBEFES). This work identified **13 suitable uses of eDNA for marine monitoring** and provides harmonised guidance to explain eDNA applications to stakeholders. It also suggests in which regulatory frameworks these applications can be integrated. This contribution can inform the development of assessment tools aligned with MSFD Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and WFD Biological Quality Elements. It can also be used to support baseline characterisation under the Nature Restoration Regulation by improving detection of rare, cryptic, and small plankton taxa. Through the development of a user-friendly brochure, **this work will offer a straightforward tool to communicate to stakeholders uniform and coherent information about eDNA applications for monitoring.**

■ The IP on **eDNA runoff bioindicators** identified a core set of microbial indicators by integrating independently generated datasets across multiple European regions. It established **standardised eDNA taxa across data set of different estuarine ecosystems** that improve transferability across Member States interface even beyond the used study cases. This work can support the use of **new microbial indicators for ecological status assessments under the WFD and enhance monitoring at the land-sea interface**, where policy implementation often faces critical data gaps.

■ The **estuarine ecological assessment using fish eDNA** applies molecular methods to monitor fish communities. This approach enables **non-invasive, repeatable sampling of fish communities that can be standardised across sites and over time**, supporting the detection of temporal trends in species presence and community structure. **The resulting eDNA-based index provides a novel method for calculating ecological status**, aligned with WFD requirements. While focused on fish, the workflow offers a transferable model for applying molecular tools also in other biodiversity assessments, **contributing to long-term, comparable monitoring under both the WFD and the MSFD**.

■ The IP on **spatial distribution of phytoplankton biomass based on remote sensing** tested and compared multiple chlorophyll-a algorithms across eight OBAMA-NEXT Learning Sites. It showcases how to leverage a centralised database of *in situ* measurements and harmonise regional approaches and achieve **more accurate and consistent estimation of coastal phytoplankton biomass from satellite data across regions**. It supports eutrophication assessments under the MSFD (Descriptor 5) and WFD by providing **harmonised, scalable methods for monitoring phytoplankton dynamics**.

■ The IP on **copepod mean size and total abundance** proposes a trait-based indicator to reflect pelagic food web dynamics. It demonstrates how **size-based indicators can complement existing metrics by capturing prey quality and energy transfer to higher levels in the food web**. It supports food web assessments under MSFD Descriptor 4 and can **contribute to the development of functional indicators for setting ecological baselines** under the NRR.

■ Coordinated efforts on **harmonisation of phytoplankton image labels** in the Baltic Sea support the integration of imaging technologies with traditional microscopy and data comparability, which supports the use of AI-based. It **contributes to preserving time series continuity and strengthens regional coordination** for MSFD and WFD implementation, as well as for HELCOM reporting.

Recommendations

Adopt new technologies of biodiversity analyses into EU policies

- Integrate cytometry, imaging, eDNA, and satellite approaches of biodiversity analyses into regulation and policies.
- Continue co-developing with specialised scientist new tools (bioindicators, map, indices, models) that could improve coastal monitoring.

Integrate small and underrepresented plankton fractions into assessments

- Develop accurate metrics for pico- and nanoplankton to ensure their inclusion in biodiversity and food web assessments.
- Use advanced tools (e.g. flow cytometry, eDNA, automated imaging) to monitor small and cryptic plankton fractions more effectively.

Promote the exploitation of existing phytoplankton long-term datasets

- Improve integration and reuse of long-term phytoplankton time series by aligning new technologies with historical and reference data.
- Support harmonisation and reanalysis of legacy datasets to establish baselines for restoration and climate-related assessments.

Establish common standards for data collection and processing

- Define and adopt best practices for plankton sampling, processing, and data storage across Europe.
- Develop validated reference datasets and incorporate non-taxonomical data (e.g. optical traits) into recognised biodiversity data infrastructures (e.g. EMODnet, OBIS).

Ensure monitoring tools are ready for policy uptake

- Expand high-quality reference libraries for marine plankton and other taxonomical groups across regions.
- Standardise sampling collections, automated analysis and data pipelines.

Improve interoperability and integration across regions and tools

- Promote intercalibration of protocols and procedures through dedicated and publicly available exercises and sites.
- Ensure integration of historical datasets into new methods to maintain continuity and avoid restarting with each technological advance.
- Support data infrastructure to facilitate sharing and aggregation.

Advance the development of policy-relevant and fit-for-purpose indicators

- Prioritise functional and size-based plankton indicators aligned with policy needs.
- Establish the standardised procedures to be able to develop new indicators based on eDNA approaches for different taxonomical groups.
- Validate new indicators against ecological thresholds and legal criteria.

Authors

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References and resources

Deliverable 6.1. Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies (<https://zenodo.org/records/13981477>)

Deliverable 2.1. Review of existing and emerging technologies for pelagic biodiversity observations (<https://zenodo.org/records/14098959>)

OBAMA-NEXT information products (<https://obama-next.eu/information-products/>)

 As this policy brief is a deliverable of the project, minor changes can be made during 2026 after the project review meeting.

For additional resources from OBAMA-NEXT project, visit the web page:
<https://obama-next.eu>

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